

PSRR Enhanced LDO Regulator Using Noise Sensing Circuit

Min-ju Kwon, Chae-won Kim, Jeong-yun Seo, Hee-guk Chae, Yong-seo Koo

Abstract—In this paper, we presented the LDO (low-dropout) regulator which enhanced the PSRR by applying the constant current source generation technique through the BGR (Band Gap Reference) to form the noise sensing circuit. The current source through the BGR has a constant current value even if the applied voltage varies. Then, the noise sensing circuit, which is composed of the current source through the BGR, operated between the error amplifier and the pass transistor gate of the LDO regulator. As a result, the LDO regulator has a PSRR of -68.2 dB at 1k Hz, -45.85 dB at 1 MHz and -45 dB at 10 MHz. the other performance of the proposed LDO was maintained at the same level of the conventional LDO regulator.

Keywords—LDO regulator, noise sensing circuit, current reference, pass transistor.

I. INTRODUCTION

WITH the advanced IC technology, the manufacturers have attention to PMIC (Power Management IC) due to the increase of the supply for the portable devices such as the cell phone, notebook using the lithium battery. Recently, the market customers require the portable devices of low power and high performance. Then, by using the only limited battery, the devices must take the functional action at the stable state for most of the operation time. Therefore, the R&D process about the high stability is necessary for the steady states using the power supply [1]-[11]. Generally, the LDO regulator is used for the stable output voltage. The linear regulator such as LDO regulator has the advantage of the low noise and the output stability. However, due to the some inevitable noise of the voltage source, LDO regulators must have the high PSRR (Power Supply Rejection Ratio).

In this paper, we proposed the LDO regulator with the enhanced PSRR using the constant current source and the noise sensing circuit.

II. THE LDO REGULATOR WITH THE NOISE SENSING CIRCUIT

A. LDO Regulator

Fig. 1 shows the structure of conventional LDO regulator. The LDO regulator is composed of the five elements: BGR, Error Amplifier, Pass transistor, Feedback Resistor and Load [12]-[14].

Min-ju Kwon, Chae-won Kim, Jeong-yun Seo, Hee-guk Chae is with the Department of Electronics & Electrical Engineering University of Dankook 126 Jukjeon-dong, Suji-gu, Yongin-si, Gyeonggi-do, 448-701 (Phone: +8231-8005-3625; fax: +8231-8005-4185; e-mail: kmz1030@naver.com).

Yong-Seo Koo* is with the Department of Electronics & Electrical Engineering University of Dankook, 126 Jukjeon-dong, Suji-gu, Yongin-si, Gyeonggi-do, 448-701, Korea (Corresponding author, e-mail: yskoo@dankook.ac.kr)

The BGR provides the constant output voltage to the input of the error amp. The error amp adjusts the gate voltage of the pass transistor with the output through the feedback for the operation as a switch. Then, the pass transistor provides the constant voltage to the load through the low voltage drop from the incoming supply voltage. Consequently, the feedback resistor senses the voltage applied to the load and feeds the error amp according to the voltage magnitude [15], [16].

Fig. 1 Structure of conventional LDO regulator

B. Noise Sensing Circuit

Fig. 2 Proposed LDO regulator block diagram

When the supply voltage fluctuates, the conventional LDO of Fig. 1 has the output voltage fluctuation causing the unstable voltage supply. For the stable power supply, the LDO regulator with the noise sensing circuit is proposed as shown in Fig. 2. The LDO regulator is composed of a reference voltage generator, an error amplifier, a pass transistor, a feedback resistor and a noise sensing circuit. The noise sensing circuit is located between the output of the error amplifier and the gate of the pass transistor. When the supply voltage is changed, the gate voltage of the pass transistor is adjusted by detecting the magnitude of the voltage difference. Then, the gate-source voltage of the pass transistor sustains the constant value and the

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(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 4 Basic properties: Phase margin, load transient, load regulation of (a), (c), (e) proposed LDO and (b), (d), (f) conventional LDO

(a)

Fig. 5 (a) PSRR of the conventional LDO (b) PSRR of the proposed LDO

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the LDO regulator with the noise sensing circuit is proposed. The noise sensing circuit can effectively control the gate biasing of the pass transistor by sensing the induced current value from the supply voltage fluctuation. The simulation is conducted with the CMOS process. As a result, the PSRR is changed from -15.1 dB to -74.6 dB, and the other properties are maintained at the same level. Therefore, the proposed circuit can supply the stable output voltage with the enhanced PSRR. In addition, the enhanced PSRR is sustained in the high frequency band.

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